

Notes

Chemical Investigation of the Bark of *Callicarpa arborea* (Verbenaceae)

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THE bark is aromatic, bitter and is applied¹ in decoction to cutaneous diseases. Since other species of *Callicarpa* are known to yield diterpenoids², we became interested to undertake a chemical investigation of the bark of the plant.

Dried and powdered bark of *C. arborea* was extracted with benzene for 10 hrs. The extract was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane and the crude methyl ester was chromatographed over deactivated alumina. Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (3:2) provided a crystalline solid which on crystallisation from methanol yielded methyl betulinate, m.p. 218°–220° (Lit.³ m.p. 220°–224°), identical, (mixed m.p. and TLC) with an authentic specimen (Found: C, 78.63; H, 10.49. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₀O₃; C, 79.10; H, 10.71%). On acetylation it furnished methyl betulinate acetate, m.p. 200°–203°, (α)_D +15.3° (Lit.³ m.p. 200°–203°, (α)_D +18°), identical (mixed m.p. and TLC) with an authentic specimen (Found: C, 77.17; H 10.06. Calc. for C₃₃H₅₂O₄; C, 77.29; H, 10.72%).

The neutral fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with a mixture of pet ether and benzene (2:3) afforded a gummy solid, m.p. 130°–132° which on acetylation and crystallisation from acetone furnished β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. 126°–128°, (α)_D +27° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 127°–128°), identical (mixed m.p. and TLC) with authentic specimen.

Further elution of the column with benzene and ether afforded a gum, which was saponified. The non-saponifiable fraction upon chromatography on silica gel gave a solid, which on crystallization from acetone furnished baurenol, m.p. 200°–203° (Lit.⁵ m.p. 206°–208°), identical (mixed m.p. and TLC) with authentic sample. (Found: C, 84.48; H, 11.57; Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O; C, 81.99; H, 11.18%).

Investigations of the other parts of the plant are in progress.

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N-Benzoyl-o-tolylhydroxylamine as a Gravimetric Reagent for Bismuth (III)

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N-BENZOYL-o-tolylhydroxylamine has been used for gravimetric determination of bismuth (III) and its separation from a large number of other ions. The precipitation of bismuth as its complex starts at pH 5.1 and is quantitative in the pH range 6.0–8.0. The creamy white precipitate can be weighed as such after drying at 110°–120° and its composition corresponds to the formula Bi(C₁₄H₁₂O₂N)₃. The interference due to Mg²⁺, As³⁺, Sb³⁺, MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻, Be²⁺, Pb²⁺, La³⁺, Th⁴⁺, UO₂²⁺, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Pd²⁺ has been avoided by working at controlled pH using suitable masking agents. The average error is generally $\pm 0.5\%$.

N-Benzoyl-o-tolylhydroxylamine has been reported as a reagent for the separation of niobium and tantalum¹, spectrophotometric determination of vanadium² and gravimetric determination of uranium³. Like N-benzoyl-phenylhydroxylamine⁴, this reagent reacts with bismuth (III) giving precipitate of definite composition.

N-Benzoyl-o-tolylhydroxylamine: The reagent was prepared by the method described earlier¹. Reagent solutions were made by dissolving it in 10–20 ml of 90% ethanol before use.

Bismuth (III) solution: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving bismuth (III) subnitrate in about 0.2M nitric acid. The metal content was determined gravimetrically⁵.

Diverse ions : Aqueous solutions of other metal ions were prepared from nitrates, chlorides or sulphates. Solutions of anions were made from the sodium, potassium or ammonium salts. A few drops of a suitable acid was added to prevent hydrolysis where necessary.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the stock solution containing 5.0 to 25.0 mg of bismuth (III), sodium potassium tartrate (3 g) solution was added. It was diluted to 200 ml and the pH was adjusted between 6.2 and 7.2 with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.0M) solution. The mixture was heated to 40°-50° and ethanolic solution of the reagent (0.21 to 0.30 g) was added dropwise with stirring. The creamy white precipitate formed was digested on hot (65°-70°) water bath for 25 to 40 mins with occasional stirring. The complex was filtered hot on a weighed gooch crucible No. 3, washed with hot (60°) water and weighed as $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ after drying at 110°-120° for 2 hrs. The metal content of the complex was obtained using a factor 0.2356.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions : Calcium, strontium and barium did not interfere. Separation of bismuth (III) from magnesium (II), arsenic (III), antimony (III), molybdenum (VI) and tungsten (VI) was possible following the procedure described above. However, 1.0 g of citric acid was added to effect separation of bismuth (III) from beryllium (II), lead (II), lanthanum (III), thorium (IV) and uranium (VI). The influence of manganese (II), cobalt (II), nickel (II), copper (II), zinc (II), cadmium (II), mercury (II) and palladium (II) was removed by adding citric acid (1.0 g) and sodium cyanide (1.0 g). Reasonable amounts of fluoride, phosphate and oxalate did not interfere with the precipitation of bismuth (III). The pH was maintained between 6.2 and 6.5 while effecting all the above separations.

Properties and composition of the complex : The creamy white bismuth (III)-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine complex melted with decomposition at 186° ± 1°. The complex was insoluble in hot (75°) water, fairly soluble in acetone, diethylether and acetic acid but slightly soluble in ethanol, methanol, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and pet-ether. It was found to be stable to (about 5N) mineral acids for few hours. The composition of the complex corresponds to the formula $\text{Bi}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_3$ in which bismuth to ligand ratio is 1 : 3 (Found : C, 56.61; H, 4.02; N, 4.77%. Calc : C, 56.82; H, 4.05; N, 4.73%).

It was found that the precipitation of bismuth (III) commenced at pH 5.1 and was quantitative in the range 6.0-8.0 and at least 125 mg excess of the reagent, in addition to the theoretical amount, was necessary for the complete precipitation of the bismuth complex.

Results showed that 5 to 25 mg of bismuth (III) could be determined accurately. Diverse ions such as Mg^{2+} , As^{3+} or Sb^{3+} (35 mg); La^{3+} or UO_2^{2+} (28 mg); MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-} , Zn^{2+} or Hg^{2+} (25 mg); Mn^{2+} or Co^{2+} (20 mg); Be^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Th^{4+} or Ni^{2+} (15 mg); Cd^{2+} (16 mg), Pd^{2+} (12 mg), Cu^{2+} (10 mg), F^- (250 mg),

PO_4^{3-} (500 mg) or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ (1000 mg) produced no influence on the precipitation of 10.16 mg of bismuth (III).

Interference : Disodium-EDTA, thioglycolic acid and large amount of fluoride interfered with the precipitation of bismuth (III) with N-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine.

Precision and Accuracy : The average error for 25 determinations of 5.0 to 25.0 mg of bismuth (III) in 200 ml was found to be ±0.5%.

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Constituents of *Seseli indicum*

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SESELI INDICUM, Wight & Arnold (*Umbelliferae*), grows generally in the plains of India. The seeds are medicinally very important¹. They act as an anthelmintic, stimulant, carminative and stomachic and are used for other purposes. Bose and Guha^{2a} isolated two coumarins, while a third was obtained by Spath *et al.*^{2b} The seeds also contain a fatty oil³ and an essential oil^{4,5}.

In view of the medicinal importance and utility of the drug a systematic chemical investigation of the dry and powdered yellowish seeds of the plant was carried out through solvent extraction, since no work appeared to have been done so far in this direction. The different extracts of the seeds obtained with petrol (60°-80°; 3.0%), benzene (4.5%), and alcohol (5.0%) were thoroughly examined. Isolation and characterisation of a number of products for the first time is reported in the present communication.

The pet.- ether extract was treated with aq. KOH (10%) and the alkali-soluble part (1.0%) on chromatography (silica gel) and crystallisation (methanol) gave a product, m.p. 83°-85° which emitted fluorescence when exposed to u.v. light. It was identified as suberosin by m.m.p. and Co-T.L.C. with an authentic specimen of the coumarin. Further elution with benzene gave bergapten (m.p.